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Membrane based purification of hydrogen system (MEMPHYS)

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ABSTRACT

A hydrogen purification system based on the technology of the electrochemical hydrogen compression and purification is introduced. This system is developed within the scope of the project MEMPHYS. Therefore, the project, its targets and the different work stages are presented. The technology of the electrochemical purification and the state of the art of hydrogen purification are described. Early measurements in the project have been carried out and the results are shown and discussed. The ability of the technology to recover hydrogen from a gas mixture can be recognized and an outlook into further optimizations shows the future potential. A big advantage is the simultaneous compression of the purified hydrogen up to 200 bar, therefore facilitating the transportation and storage.

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Introduction

Due to the increasing amount of renewable energy sources used for the generation of power in the EU, there is a current necessity for high capacity energy storage methods [1]. To address this need, many activities are underway which aim to use hydrogen as an energy storage method, for later use with renewable electrochemical energy conversion systems [2]. It is predicted that hydrogen will become a widely used energy carrier, increasing the demand for its extraction from various sources, including fossil fuels and other renewable sources.

Currently, the majority of hydrogen produced relies upon the use of large quantities of fossil fuels, such as natural gas. The achievement of high purity hydrogen is thereby associated with intensive refinery processes.

Hydrogen extracted from gas streams or storage systems is prone to be contaminated by a large variety of pollutants and

numerous purification techniques are often required to gain hydrogen, which can be consumed by renewable energy conversion systems, such as fuel cell vehicles or industrial processes etc. Therefore the project MEMPHYS, MEMbrane based Purification of HYdrogen System, targets the development of a stand-alone hydrogen purification system based on a scalable membrane hydrogen purification module. Applications are for instance hydrogen recovery from biomass fermentation, industrial pipelines, storage in underground caverns, and industrial waste gas streams.

State of the art of hydrogen purification

For the purification of hydrogen it is needed to separate hydrogen from the other substances in the gas stream. Currently, different technologies are able to extract the

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hydrogen using different characteristics of hydrogen under various conditions.

Industrial standard for the hydrogen purification is pressure swing adsorption (PSA), about 85% of the produced global hydrogen are purified by PSA [3]. At refineries PSA is used to purify reformat and to recover hydrogen from purge gas fractions from ammonia production plants. PSA uses several process steps for the purification. Most frequently eleven steps are needed, containing adsorption, cocurrent depressurization, countercurrent depressurization, countercurrent purge and the countercurrent pressurization [4]. In the first step the gas mixture has to be pressurized (up to around 40 bar) and then it is let from the bottom into the adsorber. As adsorbent serve e.g. molecular sieve, activated carbon, activated alumina or silica gel depending on the application [5]. The higher partial pressure leads to an adsorption of the impurities at the solid material. High pressure hydrogen, which is difficult to adsorb, can be recovered at the top of the adsorber. The remaining gas in the absorber is then depressurized and purged with a part of the obtained hydrogen [4]. PSA operates the adsorber beds simultaneously on a cyclic basis [5] and four to twelve columns are needed to reach an almost steady output flow of hydrogen and to meet the purity requirements [4]. PSA can reach a hydrogen purity of 99.999% [6], but can recover only 65–90% of the hydrogen [5]. PSA is suitable for a gas mixture containing 60–90 mol % hydrogen [3]. The costs of the purification process are mainly influenced by the pressure of the input gas, because the compression can lead to high costs [6]. PSA can be used for lower flow rates but because of the batch process and the huge space requirements for the columns it is impracticable and therefore also not economically viable [3,6]. When combined with for example a large ammonia production the input gas already has a higher pressure and then PSA is very efficient in terms of OPEX and CAPEX.

Cryogenic separation uses the fact that hydrogen has the lowest boiling point at minus 252.9 °C, which is below nearly all other substances. The cryogenic separation utilizes partial condensation of the foreign substances to separate the product hydrogen. Disadvantages are the high costs for the cooling, that the feed gas has to be pretreated, the process is inflexible and not as reliable as PSA or membrane processes [5,7]. A further disadvantage is that the purity of the hydrogen is limited to approximately 99% [6]. An advantage is that the hydrogen can be stored as a liquid. Because of the intensive cooling, a cryogenic separation plant is ideal for large industrial scales [6].

A third technology for hydrogen purification is by using membranes. Four different types of membranes are commercially interesting, that are polymeric membranes, porous (ceramic, carbon, metal) membranes, dense metal membranes, and ion-conductive membranes [8]. The most developed are the polymeric membranes and dense metal membranes. Both are using a pressure gradient as the driving force for the separation [8], so an input gas with a high pressure will lead to a better efficiency. These membrane systems can reach a moderate hydrogen purity of 90–95% and moderate recovery rate of 85–90% [5]. Of course a disadvantage is, that after the cleaning the hydrogen has to be compressed for transport or storage.

The existing technologies for the purification of hydrogen are only suitable for high flow rates or the resulting hydrogen has to be stored in liquid state or to be compressed afterwards. All technologies show high efficiency losses during the compression, cooling or the multi-stage process. For a smaller scale application, the hydrogen purification is often not worthwhile due to a poor ratio of costs and effort considering the high quality needs.

Electrochemical hydrogen purification

The electrochemical hydrogen purification system based on a proton exchange membrane (PEM-EHP) has the potential to fill this gap. The electrochemical principle is shown in Fig. 1. The working principle of the electrically driven electrochemical hydrogen purification and compression process consists of three steps:

- 1) Anodic, selective electro-catalysed oxidation of molecular hydrogen to protons
- 2) Subsequent migration of these protons through an electrolyte (proton exchange membrane)
- 3) Cathodic, electro-catalysed reduction of the protons back to molecular hydrogen (at elevated pressure) on the other side of the membrane.

The EHP cell is basically like a PEM fuel cell. It consists of the same components and for experiments even a fuel cell can be used. But in the working principle the EHP cell can be seen as a mixture of a fuel cell and an electrolysis cell. The processes are basically the same as in a fuel cell but unlike the fuel cell it consumes electricity to split of the hydrogen molecules.

As hydrogen is not reacting with another substance, the chemical equations are only

Like some other electrochemical converter, the PEM-EHP transports in principle only hydrogen protons and water through the membrane, which also means that all other gases stay on the anode side. The hydrogen on the cathode side is purified. In former investigations hydrogen with a purity of 97.9797% was said to be possible [9] by a recovery rate of nearly 100% [10].

The EHP is more suitable for small scale purification devices but it is also scalable to bigger demands. The one-step cleaning process includes the compression of hydrogen and therefore the technology has an advantage in efficiency compared to PSA. Furthermore because of its lower required space it can be easier integrated into existing processes.

The electrochemical principle for purification of hydrogen is mentioned and investigated for many years. The first publication known by the authors is from Sedlak, Austin and LaConti from the year 1981 [11]. In the late 1990s, Bessarabov and Rohland published about the potential of electrochemical

Fig. 1 – Electrochemical principle of the EHP.

hydrogen separation and compression [12,13], so both features of the cell are known since then.

Compression and purification of the electrochemical cell are investigated together or separately. For the compression using an electrochemical cell [13–16] should be named. The separation is considered in Refs. [17–20]. [10,21–24] are relevant for both compression and separation.

Electrochemical hydrogen compression and purification are no new technologies. Especially compression is quite reliable working and the first companies are selling an electrochemical hydrogen compressor as a product. Purification whereas is still in a research stage, because many problems still have to be solved. This concerns especially the robustness against toxic substances, the water management or the reliability. In the project MEMPHYS therefore some improvements against the state of the art will be made. Alternative catalysts will improve the tolerance against toxins, a state-of-health assessment using EIS diagnostics will help to understand the water management in the cell and can help to analyze when and why a cell is failing.

The MEMPHYS system

Project MEMPHYS develops an innovative electrochemical membrane hydrogen purification system for the extraction of hydrogen from multiple hydrogen sources and new production methods. Its unique combination of 2 membrane types, permeation-selective membrane and electrochemical membrane modules, a contaminant tolerant catalyst and an electrode cleaning method involving ozone ensures maximum flexibility and robustness for hydrogen extraction from effluents from biofermentation, industrial pipelines or from underground caverns. Detailed CFD studies result in the optimum flow field design for the targeted >90% overall recovery rate. “Round robin” testing of stack and system at different partner facilities ensures a reliable assessment of system performance and economic viability. The iterative sequence of modelling, building and

testing of EHP cell, stack and system components results in a reliable validation of a small scale hydrogen purification system at relevant conditions.

The principle of the MEMPHYS EHP system is shown in Fig. 2. A gas booster pump will take in the gas from the source and pressurize the mixture for passage through the passive perm-selective membrane to remove the majority of matrix gas and catalyst contaminants. The permeate passes a humidifier and enters the electrochemically active hydrogen purification membrane to further upgrade the purity and simultaneously compress the permeate hydrogen to 200 bar. For periodic catalyst cleaning an ozone generator is also connected to the EHP unit. The 200 bar output pressure enforces enough water condensation for the output gas stream to be dry enough to reach target hydrogen purity.

A low CAPEX for the EHP system is feasible due to the significant reductions of system costs that result from recent design improvements and market introductions of various electrochemical conversion systems such as hydrogen fuel cells.

The MEMPHYS system shall be suitable for a H₂ production rate of 5 kg/day. The inlet gas for the EHP system (which is the output gas of the specific application) should contain not less than 50% of hydrogen. The feed gas pressure can vary between 1.05 and 100 bar, depending on the application. The planned energy consumption of the system is less than 5 kWh/kg H₂. The system parameters for the MEMPHYS system are combined in Table 1.

When comparing the MEMPHYS parameters to the state of the art technologies it is getting visible that the biggest advantage of the MEMPHYS system is the combination of these parameters. PSA can efficiently produce large amounts of hydrogen per day, exemplary plants have an output of more than 67 t/day [3]. MEMPHYS, with a hydrogen production rate of 5 kg/day, therefore targets very different applications. The recovery rate of PSA is between 65 and 90% because a part of the recycled hydrogen gets lost during the purging of the absorbers. MEMPHYS whereas targets a recovery rate of above 90%. Cryogenic separation works best at a low feed gas temperature and the hydrogen has to be cooled down to minus

Fig. 2 – MEMPHYS system.

250 °C. The Pd-membrane separation whereas needs a working temperature of more than 300 °C. The MEMPHYS system works at a common temperature of 20–80 °C, which is easier to handle and the energy needed for heating or cooling is very low.

Measurement and calculation methods

Measurements were carried out in the laboratory of the DHBW. An electrochemical purification stack of the company HyET Hydrogen was used. The stack consisted of one cell, which had an industrial-standard active area. The stack was integrated in a system called MoHyTO (Mobile Hydrogen Test system for Onsite testing). This MoHyTO was developed for an easy testing at different conditions and locations and to show the compression and purification feasibility directly at the applications. The MoHyTO system contains the stack with the gas supply to the anode, a bubbler for the humidification of the gases, pipes and valves for the purging of the anode and the cathode and many regulators and sensors for the ideal operation conditions. The MoHyTO further provides the power supply and all values can be displayed and saved on the integrated computer.

For the cooling and the external gas supply, the MoHyTO was connected to a FuelCon test bench. The cooling circuit consisted of two heat exchangers, which heat or cool demineralized water, and a pump, which delivered the water to the MoHyTO. The MoHyTO was supplied with hydrogen and

nitrogen by the test bench and the needed flows were adjusted by mass flow controllers.

The operating temperature of the system was set to 35 °C, the anode pressure was around 6.5 bar and the cathode pressure 50 bar. Besides the purification of hydrogen from a mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen also a pure compression of hydrogen was performed. For the purification measurements, two gas compositions were chosen upon: 80/20% and 50/50% H₂/N₂.

The volumetric flows for the 80% hydrogen and 20% nitrogen mixture should have an amount of 0.3136 dm³/min for hydrogen and 0.0784 dm³/min for nitrogen. For the measurement of 50% hydrogen and 50% nitrogen the volumetric flows should have an amount of 0.3136 dm³/min hydrogen and 0.3136 dm³/min nitrogen and stayed constant independent of the current. In order to control the temperature of the cell within a safe range for the membrane of the EHP when operating, the measurements have been carried out up to maximum current of 45 A.

In addition to the current-voltage characteristic (IV-curve), the measurements should also determine the energy demand and the recovery rate. The specific energy demand p is calculated using Eq. (1). z is the valence, F is the faraday constant (96.485 C/mol), U the voltage and M_{H_2} the molar mass of hydrogen (2.01×10^{-3} kg/mol).

$$p = \frac{z F U}{M_{H_2}} \quad (3)$$

Resulting from the chemical equation of the anode (Eq. (1)) the valence z has a value of 2.

The recovery rate is the ratio of the net current and the nominal purification current (see Eq. (4)), which corresponds to the ratio of the molar flux \dot{n} of cathode output and anode input.

$$\text{recovery rate} = \frac{\text{net current}}{\text{nominal purification current}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{H_2, \text{Cathode}}}{\dot{n}_{H_2, \text{Anode in}}} \quad (4)$$

The net current is the subtrahend of the measured current and the back diffusion current (see Eq. (5)). The back diffusion current is assumed with 0.75 A.

$$\text{net current} = \text{measured current} - \text{back diffusion current} \quad (5)$$

Table 1 – MEMPHYS system parameters.

Parameter	Value
Feed gas pressure in bar	1.05–100
Feed gas temperature in °C	20–80
Output pressure in bar	200
Recovery rate	>90%
H ₂ production rate in kg/day	5
Energy consumption in kWh/kgH ₂ EHP stack	<3
Energy consumption in kWh/kgH ₂ system	<5
CAPEX in €/kgH ₂ /day	<1500

Eq. (6) can be used to calculate the nominal purification current. In this equation p is the pressure, \dot{V}_{H_2} the hydrogen flow rate, R the universal gas constant and T the temperature at the normal conditions of the MFC. The purification current can also be determined by a multiplication of the molar flux \dot{n} of the anode input with the valence z and the faraday constant F .

$$I_{pc} = \frac{z F p \dot{V}_{H_2}}{R T} = \dot{n}_{H_2, \text{ Anode in ZF}} \quad (6)$$

The Nernst voltage is also used for the test evaluation. This equation takes the partial pressure influence (anode and cathode hydrogen pressure and concentration) on the voltage into account. The Nernst voltage U_{Nernst} is calculated with Eq. (7). T is the temperature under operating conditions. p is the pressure at the anode or cathode.

$$U_{Nernst} = \frac{R T}{z F} \ln \frac{p_{Cathode}}{p_{Anode}} \quad (7)$$

The energy demand is mainly influenced by the mechanical strength, proton conductivity and the back diffusion of the hydrogen gas [9]. In Ref. [9] P. Bouwman describes the energy demand as a function of the compression ratio and the current density. In this investigation the anode pressure is 10 bar. For a cathode pressure of 10 bar the energy demand increases linearly in relation to the current density. This energy is fully converted into heat based on Ohm's law. With an increasing cathode pressure Nernst law and back diffusion will get more important, but to follow Bouwman at 50 bar cathode pressure the losses are nearly only heat driven.

The plotted diagrams (Figs. 3–5) based on the measurement results show an IV-curve with the current and the energy demand on the left vertical axis and the voltage on the horizontal axis. For the gas mixtures (Figs. 4 and 5) the recovery rate of the hydrogen is entered on the right vertical axis.

For the IV-curve of an EHP-cell it is important to have in mind that a steeper gradient in the course of the curve represents a lower energy demand.

Fig. 3 – Measurement results of the hydrogen compression.

Fig. 4 – Measurement results of the hydrogen purification of 80% hydrogen 20% nitrogen.

Fig. 5 – Measurement results of the hydrogen purification 50% hydrogen 50% nitrogen.

Results and discussion

Different measurements were carried out to allow a comparison of the results. In the first step hydrogen compression with only pure hydrogen was measured. With increasing voltage the current increases linearly and also the energy demand does (Fig. 3). The measurement was stopped at 45 A because of the temperature restrictions. The relating voltage was 0.12 V and the energy demand 3.19 kWh/kg. The linear increase indicates a pure Ohmic resistance during the course.

The second measurement is on the purification of a gas composition with 80% hydrogen and 20% nitrogen. At the same time the gas is compressed from 6.5 bar on the anode side to 50 bar on the cathode side.

The IV-curve, which can be seen in Fig. 4, starts at a voltage of 0.039 V. This can be justified by the fact that the activation overvoltage is present below. Up to a voltage of 0.13 V respectively 37.81 A the curve increases linearly. This is due to Ohmic losses. At this measuring point (marked with a black circle) the energy demand is 3.48 kWh/kg and 83.32% of the hydrogen is recovered. Above this measuring point the mass-transport controlled area begins which can be recognized by the decreasing ascent. Concentration and diffusion overvoltage have an influence here.

Due to the current limitation at 45 A, the curve ends at 0.171 V. At this measuring point 4.20 kWh/kg are needed to recover 99.73% of the hydrogen.

Fig. 5 shows the measurement results of the hydrogen purification of 50% hydrogen and 50% nitrogen. The IV-curve starts at a voltage of 0.045 V. The IV-curve increases linearly up to a value of 0.14 V specifically 31.28 A (lower black circle). In this first section Ohmic effects are dominating. At this measurement point 68.63% of the hydrogen was recovered by an energy demand of 3.72 kWh/kg. Above this point the mass-controlled area dominates. The current remains nearly constant from a voltage of 0.231 V and a current of 39.91 A (upper black circle). At this measuring point 88.04% of the hydrogen was recovered with an energy demand of 6.14 kWh/kg. Because of the saturation a higher recovery rate seems to be not possible.

The comparison of all three curves shows the increasing importance of the mass limitations when using an anode gas with a lower amount of hydrogen. The performance of the cell gets worse as it seems to not be possible to reach the limit of 45 A anymore, also when applying a very high voltage. At the same time the maximum recovery rate decreases by the increase of foreign substances in the anode gas. This leads to the current situation that the targets of the MEMPHYS project, which are less than 3 kWh/kg H₂ energy demand and more than 95% recovery rate at a hydrogen content of 50%, cannot be reached in the first round of measurements.

Conclusion and perspectives

Our measurements show that the technology is able to extract hydrogen from a gas mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen. The project targets are not completely achieved, but in the second iteration many optimizations will be made which will lead to better results.

For example, today the flowfield of the EHP cells is a take-over flowfield from fuel cells. Therefore, it is not designed for high differential pressures and the membrane or the gas diffusion layer is pressed into the channels. So, the maximum pressure on the cathode side of the EHP is restricted. In the next step, the ideas are to use smaller channels or to use a metal foam, which gives a better support for the membrane or the gas diffusion layer.

In addition, the measurement shows that if you would try to use the MEMPHYS system for purifying a gas mixture with a lower hydrogen content than 50%, this would strongly increase the electrical power demand or the CAPEX. The electrical power demand would increase because the diffusion of the hydrogen through the other gases would lead to higher diffusion losses. You could overcome this by increasing the active area or by increasing the number of cells you use for the stack. Both options would certainly increase the investment.

In our selected applications the gas mixtures in the anode gas are different. With the mixture of hydrogen and nitrogen the functionality of the technology itself could be shown. In the future investigations other substances in the anode gas will be tested. An important point is also the

poisoning of the catalysts by toxic substances in the gas. It is known, that if you would like to use the MEMPHYS system for purifying of a gas containing carbon monoxide (CO), the CO would block the catalyst very quickly. The catalyst could be regenerated with oxygen (O₂) or ozone (O₃), whereas the O₃ bleeding is faster than the O₂ bleeding. Therefore, it makes sense to add an ozone generator into the system. But, during the time you apply the ozone generator for the recovery of the catalyst you cannot purify hydrogen. So in this case you have to add a second EHP stack to the system, if you would like to have an almost constant output flow.

The performance of the cells within a bigger stack will be monitored by a voltage monitor to gain more information about the processes in the stack. Further optimizations will go along with a more developed flow design and an improved bipolar plate. Also, in the following measurements a multiple cells stack will be tested to gain more information about the behavior inside the stack.

We think that the EHP has many advantages compared to other technologies and the costs will decrease very much due to higher quantities of the components in the nearer future. The suitability for different applications (compression and purification) makes it a very interesting technology, especially when thinking of decentral solutions.

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